

EU-Canada alignment on digital credentials, identity and trust services

The road towards compatible and secure tools

27 February 2025 | Online Workshop

Canada and the EU have been developing comprehensive strategies on digital identity management, digital credentials and trust services. Digital identification solutions can provide safe and efficient access to public and private services such as healthcare, finance, and e-government platforms. In this respect, human-centric digital identity and digital credentials are a priority area of cooperation. Canada and the EU should continue working towards the interoperability of their trust services, which are key enablers for public administrations, business transactions and e-commerce.

Canada is currently standing up new platforms to enable a single point of access for users to sign in to government services, and for issuing and verifying digital credentials, including exploring interoperability of digital credentials across jurisdictions, leveraging global standards. In the EU, the Electronic Identification, Authentication and Trust Services (eIDAS) regulation provides a standardised framework for secure digital identification across member states, offering a cross-border, interoperable system that could serve as a model for Canada's efforts.

To further strengthen compatible solutions, this webinar seeks to promote bilateral cooperation, share best practices, and explore how regulatory provisions can be reinforced through the creation of harmonised standards under the Canada – European Union Digital Partnership.

The main goal of this Expert Workshop is to bring together representatives of different stakeholders from government, industry, academia, and other relevant institutions to identify and discuss relevant use cases and provide recommendations for a possible follow-up. Proposals for concrete actions shall be agreed upon to boost the cooperation in this important topic, reinforcing peer learning and sharing of knowledge.

The discussions within this workshop are part of a broader framework, the EU-Canada Digital Partnership, launched in 2023, which serves as a key instrument to foster cooperation on digital issues. This partnership extends beyond information exchange, driving concrete initiatives in the digital economy with measurable outcomes. Cooperation on international standards plays a crucial role in supporting the development of a human-centric digital identity and digital credentials. A significant focus has been placed on the development of pilot projects aimed at enhancing interoperability, laying the groundwork for potential mutual recognition. Insights from this workshop will also contribute to the upcoming Ministerial-level Digital Partnership Council, expected to convene in Canada in the upcoming months, reinforcing the shared values and challenges between Canada and the EU in the digital domain.

EU-Canada alignment on digital credentials, identity and trust services
27 FEBRUARY 2025 | 15:00-17:15 (CET)

17 ETFs Members

92 Registrants

Gender

79% 21%

Participants by country

Participants by domain

Represented Stakeholders

Event Takeaways:

The EU and Canada are aligning frameworks to ensure interoperability and mutual recognition of digital credentials, with collaboration on international standards being key to fostering a trusted, privacy-focused, and human-centric digital identity ecosystem.

In Canada, digital credentials complement traditional methods, offering citizens and businesses a secure and convenient alternative. Their applications span multiple sectors, including travel, driver's licenses, and academic diplomas. To enhance user experience, the government prioritizes seamless access, ensuring citizens can use a single, interoperable digital wallet instead of managing multiple systems.

The EU Digital Identity Wallet prioritizes security and privacy, ensuring personal data protection while facilitating the use of digital identities for both public and private services across the EU.

The EU and Canada both prioritize privacy, security, and openness, which fosters alignment on digital credentials. However, fragmented standards pose challenges to interoperability. To create a trusted and seamless ecosystem, strong international collaboration among standardization bodies is crucial.

Event Takeaways:

Although there are challenges in harmonizing various standards for digital credentials and identity systems, such as mobile driver's licenses and verifiable credentials, there is a consensus that mutual cooperation and alignment are essential to ensure interoperability, particularly between the EU and Canada.

Ensuring cross-border interoperability between different identity and trust frameworks, particularly between Canada and the EU, is a significant challenge. Developing mutual recognition mechanisms and conformity assessment frameworks is essential. These processes ensure that digital credentials issued in one jurisdiction, such as a Canadian province or EU country, are recognized and accepted by others, supporting global scalability and trust in digital identity systems.

Developing universal, repeatable frameworks for digital identity and standards that extend beyond bilateral agreements is crucial. The focus should be on creating legal and technical solutions that enable global interoperability, such as model laws for cross-border identity management.

While digital credentials may seem like a technical topic, they have real-world applications that can simplify interactions between citizens, businesses, and governments. Future work should focus on practical implementations that demonstrate interoperability.

Insights from the experts:

"The digital partnership goes well beyond information exchanges; it really covers a number of initiatives on the digital economy. It's a collaboration vehicle to have very, very concrete deliverables in the many areas that it covers."

Gabriele Bertolli - Deputy Head of Unit, European Commission, DG CNECT/D3

"Standardization, and especially digital standardization, has become a matter of geopolitical interest in recent years. One of the strong components of this goal is to align and join efforts with like-minded partners that share our common values and interests, and of course, Canada is one of our closest allies."

Carlos Lopez Rodriguez - EC DG CNECT Policy Officer, ICT Standardisation Sector

"Citizens, when they request their wallet, will have three key functionalities: identification, storing and sharing of data, and the ability to perform the highest quality electronic signatures."

Vincente Andreu Navarro - European Commission, DG CNECT/H4 (eGovernment and Trust)

"Digital credentials are an opportunity to increase privacy protection security, giving end users more control over their information and who they share it with; from a service provider standpoint it gives us greater certainty, it makes it much easier for us to detect fraud and to verify that the things are authentic"

Paul Jackson - Director of Government of Canada Issue and Verify (Digital Credentials) at the Canadian Digital Service

"The EUID wallet is a legal framework, but there is also a technical framework. So essentially, there might be different implementations of the wallet, but all of them have to follow the same requirements, the same specifications. And we agree by drafting a list of requirements in a collaborative way."

Paolo de Rosa - European Commission, DG CNECT/H4 (eGovernment and Trust)

"Next Generation internet is an initiative with a focus on creating a human Centric internet, reimagining the internet as a humanic internet, and also on developing these key technical components that are aligned also with the EU digital rights and values."

Stergios Tsiafoulis - Programme and Policy Officer, European Commission, DG CNECT/E3 (Next-Generation Internet)

"We were approached about NGI Sargasso to focus on the travel continuum. The scenario is about a Canadian tourist booking a vacation in Austria, with two use cases. This is to show what a traveler might experience and how to solve the challenges one might face through the use of a Digital Wallet."

Ben Piercey - CTO, Co-founder, AffinitiQuest

Insights from the experts:

"Standard does not equal interoperability is a very important and big message. We're learning this all the time when we're working in projects like this or in the EU large scale Pilots where we're also demonstrating interoperability with other vendors or when we're working in projects maybe outside of Europe with large US companies that have similar product offerings, it's just really difficult."

Dominik Beron - Co-Founder & CEO, walt.id

"I believe that sometimes unfortunately there is competition between standard bodies and not perfect communication about what each standard is doing. Making these standards compatible and interoperable is not easy and cannot be easily justified on a technical level— Interoperability is hard to achieve."

Markus Sabadello - Founder Danube Tech, INSTAR Cybersecurity/eID Task Force

"It's simple in many respects, standards are reviewed whenever their context changes. In this regard the suite of standards from ETSI on eIDAS are being expanded to address the policy and technical requirements from eIDAS2 arising from the expansion of application of eID and the use cases that arise, especially where eIDAS intersects with other legislation such as the data act, and of course with the wider proliferation of an e-enabled world. Flexibility is the keyword."

Scott Cadzow - ETSI ISG ETI Chair, INSTAR Cybersecurity/eID Task Force

"There has been a similar exercise between the US NIST and the EU Commission last year, where they analyzed and compared eIDAS LoA with NIST SP 800-63. The report was called "EU-US TTC Digital Identity Mapping". The key takeaway from this report is that the EU's eID schemes are mainly driven by the eIDAS regulation, whilst the US is more focused on guidelines."

Sebastian Elfors - CEN/TC 224/WG 20 European Digital Identity Wallet

"International agreements and technical standards are developed with reliability as the first priority and interoperability as the second. Their legal effects are left to individual nations. The focus is not just on whether a system is reliable or interoperable, but on how rights are protected and how jurisdictional matters will be addressed."

Tim Bouma - Special Advisor, Digital Governance Council

"Digital credentials, digital identities, enable us to facilitate our interaction with public administration or to do things to engage between businesses, to have something with commercial benefit for both citizens and businesses."

Costas Kapsouropoulos - Digital Counsellor of the EU Delegation to Canada

**Watch the
recording!**

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INSTAR EU-Canada alignment on Digital Identification (eID)

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